

Deliverable No. 6.4

DiscardLess

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Deliverable 6.4

Economic feasibility study for the best use of unavoidable unwanted catches, avoiding creating incentives to the fisheries

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Summary of D6.4.

Economic feasibility study for the best use of unavoidable unwanted catches, avoiding creating incentives to the fisheries.

This document is the fourth deliverable in work package six (WP6) of the DiscardLess project, which aims to contribute to the gradual elimination of the discards in the European fisheries, in agreement with the reformed Common Fisheries Policy (CFP) of the EU and the implementation of the landing obligation (LO).

The LO states that all regulated species shall be landed. This implies developing alternative solutions at land to manage and make best use of Unavoidable Unwanted Catches (UUC). However, the CFP also states that these solutions shall avoid incentivising the targeting of fishing on these UUC.

On the other hand, the handling of UUC onboard will increase onboard handling, which is already time consuming and demanding for the crew. This will increase costs. Shortage of storage capacity because of the space needed for UUC onboard may also contribute to reducing income, therefore viable solutions for UUC management are needed to minimise the impact of the LO on the industry.

The suggested uses of unavoidable unwanted catches reported in deliverable D6.2. need thus to be economically attractive for the processors and for the fishers and at the same time must avoid creating incentives to the fisheries.

The present deliverable 6.4 looks into some of the initiatives that have actually already taken place using the UUC as raw-material. To get an overview of the amount of UUC landed and of what would be viable options for the processing industry, and to collect data needed for the cost-benefit analyses of the options, many interviews were performed in the three countries of Denmark, France and Spain. The overall conclusion of all the interviews is that no product is currently made from a single source of UUC, but the landed UUC are integrated in the raw-material stream of the processing industries, especially fish meal and fish oil industries.

Box 1: Report Highlights

There is a broad range of possibilities to valorise UUC fish and fish compounds, however, not all the solutions are able to cope with the huge variability of the expected UUC landings.

The LO states that only UUC above Minimum Conservation Reference Size (MCRS) can be used for human consumption. There is a need for designing new fish products that avoid incentivising the catching of undersized fish, and, at the same time, avoid affecting negatively the existing markets.

A more in-depth analysis of the economic feasibility of some of the valorisation options for different UUC fractions in different scenarios (D6.2) has been performed.

For the Bay of Biscay case study (BoB-CS), some fish species as mackerel, horse mackerel and blue whiting have important volumes of discards due to their low commercial value. They are thus considered as UUC for which better commercialization and consumption could be enhanced by developing new seafood products or concepts.

Also, in the Bay of Biscay, there is an important amount of hake under MCRS that can't be used in direct human consumption but can be very valuable for the production of food ingredients such as flavouring agents.

Finally, the production of fishmeal and fish oil used for animal feed, mainly for aquaculture, is the most common use of fish by-products and is a straightforward option for the treatment of UUC when there is an available facility nearby.

The feasibility study indicates that the proposed solutions are economically feasible within the scope of the study even at low price.

The North Sea case study describes the activities taking place in the Danish port of Hanstholm, with a case study on the fishery targeted at plaice. Several interviews with relevant buyers of the UUC were conducted and their evaluation is presented.

Box 2: The methods/approaches followed

The expected amount of potential UUC in the different CS were quantified based on current discards data, and the most favourable valorisation options were selected based on their economic feasibility.

For various solutions the economic analysis was performed through calculation of the Benefit-Cost Ratio (BCR), Net Present Value (NPV), Internal Return Rate (IRR), etc. Due to the important variation of the amount of UUC foreseen, several scenarios were evaluated.

Furthermore, the calculation of UUC price range was performed to reach a “non incentivising” scenario.

The North Sea case study is based on personal interviews with relevant persons from the processing and final product links in the value chain.

Box 3: How these results can be used and by who?

The results from the economic evaluation of different valorisation option can be used by:

- Research centres to contrast different solutions and compare with its own
- Fishermen organization willing to evaluate the value of their UUC
- Local companies: fish processing industries, “waste” managers looking for improving their fish by products or the UUC
- Investor willing to start a new business
- Local administration bodies to develop integrated valorisation plans for discards
- Policy makers to promote the implementation of selected strategies

In general, the economic feasibility of a technically viable solution is of great interest for any actor of the chain looking for a solution to minimize the economic impact of the LO application.

Box 4: Policy Recommendations

Due to economic viability of the proposed valorisation schemas for UUC can be proposed for the definition of best available techniques.

Changes in the CFP regarding proper on board handling and storage of UUC can help obtain more value from these fractions.

Abbreviations	
BoB	Bay of Biscay
BCR	Benefit cost ratio
CFP	Common Fishery Policy
CS	Case Study
EU	European Union
IRR	Internal Rate of Return
LO	Landing Obligation
MCRS	Minimum Conservation Reference Size
NPV	Net Present Value
PP	Payback Period
ROI	Return on Investment
UUC	Unavoidable, Unwanted Catches
WP	Work Package

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1 Introduction

The Common Fisheries Policy (CFP) of the European Commission introduced in 2013 a discard ban which states that all catches of species subjected to catch quotas and/or Minimum Conservation Reference Size (MCRS) will have to be landed and will be counted against quota.

The discard ban, or Landing Obligation (LO), is being gradually implemented between 2015 and 2019, after which all EU fisheries are required to land all catches. During that period, stakeholders may explore and put into practice different strategies, first to minimize the discards, and second, to find the most adequate uses for unavoidable unwanted catches (UUC) subjected to the landing obligation in order to limit the impact that the LO may have in the harbours and local economies.

This report is the fourth deliverable in work package six (WP6) of the DiscardLess project, which deals with the impacts and challenges that the new policy may cause on land.

To evaluate and overcome the possible challenges, the following specific objectives are addressed in this WP:

- 1) Analysing the potential availability of UUC in specific harbours;
- 2) Evaluating most suitable uses of UUC;
- 3) Constructing an initial selection of potential uses and solution approach;
- 4) Ensuring traceability and market acceptance of the products resulting from UUC valorisation;
- 5) Obtaining a clear and convincing picture of the economic profile and the feasibility of the implementation of the proposed solutions;
- 6) Validating the solution proposed for best use of UUC by a pilot trial;

In particular, this current deliverable D6.4 deals with the economic feasibility study for the best use of unavoidable unwanted catches, avoiding creating incentives to the fisheries.

In the planning stage of the DiscardLess project, it had been anticipated that a reasonable quantity of former discarded fish would be landed already within the first years of implementation. We expected that we would have several examples to deal with, so we could calculate the costs and benefits of landing the UUC. In the present deliverable, two examples are given to show what happened in reality and why it was not possible to make realistic economic studies. The amounts of UUC, which have been landed after the introduction of the Landing Obligation, are negligible and totally unfit for any calculations. But there has been no observations of positive profits in the landing of UUC fishes.

For different case studies, best valorisation possibilities were described in D6.2. This deliverable presents a more precise evaluation of their economic feasibility.

2 Current uses during the implementation of the LO

During the period 2015-2018, and before the full implementation of the landing obligation, a transition period was expected to occur with some UUC being landed and some infrastructures being adapted. Some examples are presented below.

2.1 Example A: Baltic cod, Denmark

One of the first geographical areas where the Landing Obligation was introduced was the Baltic Sea. The fishing activities in the Baltic are concentrated on cod, herring and flatfish species. The Minimum Conservation Reference size (MCRS) for cod was initially lowered from 38 cm to 35 cm, which reduced the former discard fraction by more than 50 %. At the beginning of 2016 some effort were made by several vessels to land their discards, and they landed up to 50 kg of undersized cod per fishing trip at the island of Bornholm. Fishers asked the fishery inspection about what to do with these amounts; the answer was either to discard them as the former practice or to send them with the lorries transporting part of the landings to the fish auctions in the western part of Jutland – a journey of more than 550 km including a ferry crossing and two toll bridges. The transport raised questions such as, if these fish should be separated from the rest of the transported fish for human consumption, but the fishermen were told that separate fish boxes were sufficient. Reaching the destination, the undersized fish were delivered to the fish meal and oil factory. The payment to the fishermen did not even cover the transportation costs. So, in this case, there is no need to make a cost-benefit analysis, because the result is negative and a direct cost to the fishermen. Payment from the factory is e.g. around 1.80 DKK/kg, expenses box rent, transport etc. e.g. is around 2.00 DKK.

The official amount of undersized cod was in 2017 14 tons. The actual observed amount based on observers onboard the fishing vessels is 1400 tons². So the majority of the UUC is still dumped as discard. The 14 tons were landed and brought to the feed processing plants, mainly in North and West Jutland. The fish were transported un-iced and unsorted, and this, together with the very small amounts per transportation, made them totally unfit for anything else than reducing to fish meal and fish oil. No other serious buyers have been interested in these UUC fishes.

There have been initiatives to start silage of the UUC fishes with other fish species and of the guts from the slaughtered fish. Some economic calculations were performed for having the proper equipment on the quayside of the landing port of the island of Bornholm and the Koege harbor on the island Zealand. But after some preliminary studies the plans have been abandoned, because it would have been a negative outcome of the investment. Just buying the formic acid to be used for the silage process would have made the calculation negative. Formic acid is mandatory if the silage has to be processed as fish meal and fish oil or as feed products.

² <https://www.dr.dk/nyheder/penge/s-og-df-kraever-kontrol-af-fiskere-kun-boeder-ulovligt-udsmid-af-fisk>

The fishing vessel HG 306 Tobis of Hirtshals, was in 2015 equipped with special tanks for keeping silage onboard and facilities to administrate the formic acid. The volume of the silage tanks were the same as a tank-lorry's loading capacity (22 tons), so no empty volume were transported. The skipper of the fishing vessel tried a few times to use the system in the Baltic, when they were fishing flounder. But there was no positive economy output from these experiments and the activities were dropped.

HG 306 Tobis

2.2 Example B: Plaice in the North Sea and Skagerrak, Denmark

The Landing Obligation was introduced in the North Sea and Skagerrak in 2016, but only for a few fish species. Among them plaice caught with large mesh size trawl (TR1).

The biggest harbor for fish for human consumption is Hanstholm in the North-west of Denmark. The fish auction are selling fish landed by Danish fishermen, but also fish caught by fishermen from Norway, Scotland, the Netherlands and France. The Port of Hanstholm that owns all the buildings for the auction and the cooling facilities etc. was very keen of making the best possible solutions for the fishing vessels landing UUC. Because it was impossible to have reliable information from the authorities regarding storage methods, cooling, icing, separation from fish for human consumption, the construction work was postponed. This was an economically wise decision, because the landed UUC fish in 2017 were negligible. There has now been constructed a separate room back to back to the fish auction, but at the moment this room only functions as a interim storage room for the few boxes that have to be picked up by the lorry that transport offal from the processing industries to the mink feed factories. The facilities are there and waiting to be used.

In a national project affiliated to DiscardLess, a trawler from the harbor of Hanstholm was involved in a series of observed fishing trips for catching plaice. The trawler is HM 120 Astoria of Hanstholm.

HM 120 Astoria

The original plan of the project was to rebuild the processing deck, so that all the new amount of UUC could be handled in an ergonomically way and to store this fraction of the catch in a proper manner. The first fishing trips with observer onboard were conducted in 2016, when plaice under the reference measurement had to be landed accordingly with the Landing Obligation. The result was 24 kg of undersized plaice out of a total catch of 11 tons. This result stopped all activities to rebuild the vessel, because it would have been an “overkill” action in investment. In 2017 the fishing trips were repeated, but no changes were observed in the plaice catches that could justify an investment of 500.000 DKK. There were a slightly higher bycatch of small cod, but not much. It was decided to repeat the fishing trips with observer in 2018.

HM 120 Astoria fishing activities in 2016. The red ring is where the fishing trips with observer onboard took place.

Fishing activities in the Baltic Sea are targeted at cod and are not included in the case study.

2.3 Example C: Observation of the Basque Fleet in Bay of Biscay

The main port in the basque country with regards to discards potentially landed is Ondarroa. From the historical data more than 3000 tonnes per year of UUC could be expected to be landed (cf deliverable D6.1).

With this information in mind, several refrigerated rooms were installed in different locations to store and facilitate the logistic process and fishmeal processors expressed interest in these potential UUC.

However, during the transition period only negligible amounts of UUC have been landed.

2.4 Example D: Other ongoing initiatives in Europe

Several interviews were conducted with keypersons from the UUC value chain both in Denmark and in the most important fishing nations in the EU (except the UK). The overall conclusion is that all potential receivers of the UUC catch are willing to buy the fish, if the quality and price are reasonable compared to other raw-material supplies.

2.4.1 The Danish UUC value chain

In the Danish UUC value chain, the main buyers are the feed producers, either as fish meal and fish oil producers which produce part of the ingredients of the final feed, or as directly feed producers as the mink feed producers. One of the largest operators among the Danish Fish Meal and Fish Oil producers is FF-Skagen. They know that a very small fraction of their raw-material is landed as UUC, but it is mixed in their normal raw-material streams. No doubt that they can take the entire amount that is landed as UUC. The price varies (following world-wide global price), but UUC will be in the lower end of the price spectrum, because it is whole un-gutted fish and maybe not even iced (around 1,50 DKK/kg). The highest price is white fish, well iced and only one or two days old (1,70 DKK/kg). Prime silage will be paid with 1,80 DKK/kg. The actual prices are not as important as the differences between the different categories.

Denmark is the biggest producers of mink fur in the world with approx. 1.500 farmers producing 19 mill pelts per year. Year 2016 – 17 have seen a decline in the production, but the producers are still optimistic. The feed for the mink is produced in 14 different feed-units, all of them individually owned by local cooperatives of producers. Approx. 40 % of the feed is fish, either fresh or frozen, landed in Denmark or brought from e.g. Iceland or the Faeroe Islands. The mink feed producers require the best handled raw-material, because the minks only thrive on fresh fish. That way the mink feed producers pays a higher price per kg. They can take all the UUC that can be landed – if it has the right quality.

The pet-food industry is one of the rapid growing branches in the world. The producers are mainly large international feed-producers; several are in Germany and the Netherlands. These producers normally use fish meal and fresh small fish cut in pieces. There are several smaller pet-food producers in Denmark, which use whole fresh fish or rest-material from the filleting industry.

Dry feed for animals normally contain fish meal and sometimes fish oil from the fish meal and fish oil producers – so they do not care of the origin of the product. Another and rapidly growing segment is the dedicated feed producers that are making high-end products for the pets. The price per kg is high and they could be interested in high quality UUC fish. One of the focus areas of the pet-food producers is the content of heavy metals, because the pet owners are afraid of bioaccumulation of these metals in their animals. The pet-food producers prefer fatty fishes due to content of polyunsaturated fatty oils, but there could be some issues in particular with Baltic UUC, which would be fatty fishes but also with risks of high contents of heavy metals and PCB. The pet-food producers normally pay the same price for the raw-material as the mink producers.

Henne Pet Food – one of the interviewed Danish producers are producing food for dogs, cats and supplements of fish oil for pets. Are using heads of salmon and other fish species that are smoked.

2.4.2 Interviews with keypersons from the EU fish value chain in 2016.

Interviews with keypersons from the EU fish value chain were conducted in the late 2016.

Boulogne-Sur-Mer is the biggest harbor in France in terms of landings. There are six large trawlers landing fresh iced fish and four landing frozen fish. There are 90 medium and small vessels, which primarily fish in the English Channel area – the fleet landed in 2015 36.000 tons of fish. Boulogne-Sur-Mer has a cluster of processing and support industries, which handle more than 330.000 tons of imported fish from primarily Denmark, Norway, UK, Ireland, Island and others. The conclusion of the interviews were that only very limited amounts of UUC fish are landed. The landed UUC fish is sold to the local industry Copalis, which has specialized in producing health products, cosmetics and fish

meal and fish oil. This company gets their raw-material from all over France. The price paid to the fishermen varies, but is regulated in accordance with the price of raw-material for the fish meal and fish oil industry.

Photo of the medium trawler of Boulogne-Sur-Mer. Photo Kasper Aalling Teilmann, Gemba Seafood A/S

Interviews done in Vigo, Spain showed the same tendencies as in both Denmark and France. The biggest operator in Spain is Pescanova, but they import and catch all their fish outside the EU. If their fishing fleet catches fish that fall under the EU Landing Obligation, these fish are sold outside the EU.

At a meeting with OPROMAR (Organización de Productores de Pesca Fresca del Puerto y Ria de Marin) – a producers organization for fresh fish-trawlers, purse seiners and longline fishing vessels, it appeared clearly that this organization was very keen to get the highest profit out of the UUC fish. They have established a project called “Descartes.cero” and the main focus is underutilized fish species and UUC fish. They are just waiting for the UUC fish to be landed.

3 Economic feasibility study for the best use of UUC

3.1 Bay of Biscay case study

Taking in to consideration the main discards recorded in the Bay of Biscay (BoB), and the methodology for the selection of best valorisation options described in D6.2, different approaches were analysed more in/depth:

- New food products: Fish-burger from minced fish products for mackerel
- New food ingredients: Protein hydrolysate for hake
- High quality feed: General management in fishmeal facilities

3.1.1 Methodology

The economic feasibility of the different scenarios was performed through the calculation of the Benefit-Cost Ratio (BCR), Net Present Value (NPV), Internal Return Rate (IRR), and other economic criteria. When necessary to address the uncertainty of estimates used in economic analysis, a scenario analysis was conducted to assess the impact of primary variables on economic feasibility.

3.1.1.1 Benefit cost ratio

A benefit cost ratio (BCR) aims to identify the relationship between the cost and benefits of a proposed project. The BCR is calculated by dividing the benefits by the costs.

If a project has a BCR that is greater than 1, it indicates that the NPV of the project benefits outweigh the NPV of the costs. Therefore, the project can be considered economically feasible if the value is significantly greater than 1. If the BCR is equal to 1, the ratio indicates that the NPV of expected profits equal the costs. If a project's BCR is less than 1, the project's costs outweigh the benefits and should not be considered feasible.

3.1.1.2 Net Present Value

The Net Present Value (NPV) is a formula used to determine the present value of an investment by the discounted sum of all cash flows received from the project.

The formula for NPV is:

$$NPV = \sum_{t=0}^T \frac{C_t}{(1+r)^t} - C_0$$

Where:

- C_t = net cash inflow (FCF) during the period t
- C_0 = total initial investment costs
- r = discount rate
- t = number of time periods

If $NPV > 0$ means that the investment would produce profits above the required profitability (r). The project is feasible.

If $NPV < 0$ means that the investment would produce losses below the required profitability (r). The project should be rejected.

3.1.1.3 Internal Return Rate

Internal Rate of Return (IRR) is a metric used to estimate the profitability of an investment. IRR is a discount rate that makes the NPV of all cash flows from the studied scenario equal to zero.

To calculate IRR, one would use the NPV formula, set it equal to zero and solve for the discount rate r . Because of the nature of the formula, IRR cannot be calculated analytically, and must be estimated through iterations, using, for example, the solver-tool of Excel.

The higher a project's IRR, the more desirable it is to undertake. IRR is uniform for investments of varying types and, as such, IRR can be used to rank multiple prospective projects a firm is considering on a relatively even basis. Assuming the costs of investment are equal among the various projects, the project with the highest IRR would probably be considered the best and undertaken first.

3.1.1.4 Return On Investment

The Return On Investment (ROI) is a performance indicator used to evaluate the efficiency of an investment or to compare the efficiency of different investments.

To calculate ROI, the benefit of an investment is divided by the cost of the investment, and the result is expressed as a percentage or a ratio.

3.1.1.5 Payback Period

The payback period (PP) is the length of time required to recover the cost of an investment. The payback period ignores the time value of money (TVM), unlike other methods of capital budgeting such as net present value (NPV), internal rate of return (IRR), and discounted cash flow. It is calculated by:

$$PP = \text{years full recovery} + \frac{\text{unrecovered cost at the beginning of last year}}{\text{cash flow in following year}}$$

The payback period of a given investment or project is an important determinant of whether to undertake the project, as longer payback periods are typically not desirable for investment positions. So, the shorter the payback period of a project, the more attractive the project will be to investors.

3.1.1.6 Scenario analysis

Generally speaking, a scenario analysis is a technique used to determine how different values of an independent variable impact a particular dependent variable under a given set of assumptions.

In an economic feasibility study, this technique can be used to evaluate different scenarios, changing one or more input variables, such as the amount of raw material or their price, to estimate their impact in the profitability of the proposed solution.

3.1.2 New fish products

The main interest of this development was the introduction of new seafood products derived from mackerel (*Scomber spp*) into menus for children, teenagers and seniors. This objective has a social aspect, and deals also with the industrial feasibility and sustainability of a high nutritional and sensory quality fish species from the Northwestern Cantabrian Fishery.

a) Social objective: promotion of healthy consumption by children and teenagers, by increasing the variety of fish from local origin available in school menus, introducing new references of fish products not categorized as precooked. That means increasing the offer of convenient mackerel fish products, ready to eat in the Retail market for healthy eating and conscious consumers.

b) Industrial feasibility objective: Analysing at industrial scale-up the technical and economic feasibility of transformation processes previously developed on a pilot scale, testing and validating the products in real conditions of commercialization.

3.1.2.1 Fish mince elaboration at industrial scale

Following the optimization of the processing at pilot-scale, frozen mackerel was processed at pre-industrial scale-up to optimize the control parameters of the filleting and pulp processing process. Several production batches were carried out collecting information of yields and operational costs (labour, energy costs, etc ...).

Figure 1: Steps at industrial scaling-up of the mincing process

Processing capacities for mincing were adjusted according to the labour and yield during the project to achieve a final capacity of 200-250 kg/hour for frozen fish and 100-125 Kg mince/hour. The mince yield obtained in the different batches was about 50 %.

3.1.2.2 Fish products

This fish mince as raw material was included in the preparation of different solutions or alternatives of fish products from mackerel, horse mackerel and blue whiting developed at pilot and pre-industrial scale: chilled packaged fish burgers, frozen ball shaped fish products with sauce filling and frozen fish sticks with cheese filling.

The forming technology Rheon was used to elaborate these products at pilot scale optimizing formulation of fish minces to obtain suitable physico-chemical and texture properties (hardness, viscosity, cohesiveness, humidity, fat) to feed the coextrusion equipment.

Figure 2: Products developed by application of Rheon technology at AZTI pilot facilities.

Figure 3: Pasteurized fish burgers process flow diagram.

Following the trials at pre-industrial scale, manufacturing costs (excluding factory costs) were estimated for three fish products from mackerel: fish mince and fish burgers; two burger tray chilled and frozen burgers.

3.1.2.3 Economic aspects

3.1.2.3.1 Investment

For the processing of fish into fish mince, fish-burger, or the inclusion of a new processing line in an existing fish-processing facility, the following equipment are needed:

Table 1: Prices of equipment for fish mince and fish hamburger production

Equipment	€
Frozen storage room	28,000
Refrigerated storage room	15,000
Automatic fish feeding machine	60,000
Heading, gutting, filleting	200,000
Mince separator	53,000
Weighing scale	1,600
Cutting/mixing machine	70,000
Automatic casing machine	30,000
Vacuum/MAP packing machine	25,000
Horizontal Batch retort	240,000

This will suppose an investment of about 722,600 € for a production of 1,000 Kg/day of processed fish products considering that the final product marketed is fish burger.

Three different scenarios can be feasible:

- 1- Production of fish mince as final product for the HORECA (Hotel/Restaurant/Café) market.
- 2- Production of fish burger for HORECA market.
- 3- Production of a two burgers tray pack (180 g) for RETAIL.

The first solution would suppose the creation of a new business for processing of fresh or frozen mackerel into fish mince. In the second scenario the implementation of a new line of fish processing in a fish transformation factory industry and in the third case the development of a new fish processing line (burger fish tray) in a convenience food products industrial company.

In these last situations some of the equipment already existing in the industry could be used for the new products so the investment would be minimal.

3.1.2.3.2 Costs

The production of the different products implies several costs such as:

- Raw material and ingredients costs: Fish and ingredients
- Packaging costs: plastics, film, labelling
- Labour costs: filleting, mincing, mixing, shaping, packaging, pasteurizing cleaning

Table 2 groups the costs for each category.

Table 2: Main figures of fish mince, fish burger and final product prices.

MANUFACTURING COSTS (€)			
MACKEREL PRODUCT	FISH MINCE	FISH BURGER HORECA	FISH BURGER RETAIL
€	Kg	Kg	PACK (180 g) Kg
DIRECT MATERIAL COSTS Fish and ingredients	1.6 €	1.963 €	0.558 € 3.191 €
DIRECT MATERIAL COSTS Packaging: plastics, film, labelling	0.025 €	0.103 €	0.280 € 1.597 €
LABOUR COSTS: filleting, mincing, mixing, shaping, packaging, pasteurizing cleaning.	0.525 €	0.107 €	1.189 € 6.795 €
TOTAL	2.152 €	2.173 €	2.027 € 11.583 €

For the foodservice sector and especially considering school menus, possible market competitors for mackerel burgers (estimated market price 5.00 € / Kg) would be fatty fish species as frozen tuna, fresh salmon trout and fresh / frozen salmon, with indicative market prices of about;

- Frozen tuna from 6.74 to 8.90 € / Kg (without VAT).
- Salmon trout from 4.89 to 5.20 € / Kg (without VAT).
- Salmon from 10.14 to 17.81 € / Kg (without VAT).

Increasing the consumption of fatty fish species as a way of health promotion in the European consumers is a concern issue for administrations and governments. Introduction of healthy, safe (no bones) and convenience products from mackerel would be an opportunity for the different food market channels.

3.1.2.3.3 Economic feasibility.

Taking into account the investment needed with a 10 years depreciation period and a 5 % discount rate and loan rate, the costs of the process and the expected incomes for a yearly production of 250 tn burger-fish the different economics parameters can be calculated for different scenarios.

If we suppose that the production line is based on a previously existing facility,

Table 3: Main economic feasibility figures for the production of fish burger in an existing facility

Parameter	Unit	Value
Production (tn/year)	tn/year	250
Total Expenses	€	692,599
Total Incomes	€	1,250,000
BCR		1.80
NPV	€	4,180,859
IRR	%	83.7
ROI	%	87.1
PP	years	1.21

Table 4: Main economic feasibility figures to produce fish burger in a new facility

Parameter	Unit	Value
Production (tn/year)	tn/year	250
Total Expenses	€	710,999
Total Incomes	€	1,250,000
BCR		1.75
NPV	€	3,965,234
IRR	%	67.5
ROI	%	71.1
PP	years	1.50

Both scenarios give very good results, slightly better if we introduce a new line in an existing facility, being the investment very profitable, with an excellent payback period of less than 2 years.

3.1.3 New food additives

As fish under MRCS cannot be used for direct human consumptions other uses have to be foreseen for these by-catches. In Bay of Biscay this is of particular importance for the Hake that account for 300 tn/year and mainly small size.

The production of flavouring agents has been successfully tested and the economics aspects of such options has been evaluated.

The flavour of seafood is influenced by a variety of volatile and non-volatile flavour components. Nonvolatile compounds such as free amino acids, peptides, organic bases and acids, nucleotides, sugars, and inorganic salts influence the taste whereas volatile compounds are responsible for the aroma. Flavorants with characteristic seafood flavour can be produced by enzymatic hydrolysis of UUC. Amino acids and peptides are released during hydrolysis and influence the taste of the flavourings, while volatile degradation compounds generated in the process give the aroma.

Traditionally endogenous proteolytic enzymes were used to obtain fish sauce or silage product, but the use of specifically designed enzymes improves the process control and the product replicability. These fish protein hydrolysate can be obtained from any species, from fish muscle, whole fish or fish by-products. There is no need for previous transformation although previous drying would be advisable in order to reduce transport costs. Raw material should be stored in refrigerated conditions or frozen, and histamine production should be carefully controlled.

3.1.3.1 The process

The production of flavouring agents consists in the obtaining of a fish protein hydrolysate through a controlled enzymatic process. Proteases, such as Novozymes Flavourzyme®, provide a deep hydrolysis of proteins to generate high-quality flavour. If a more extensive hydrolysis is needed to solubilize a substrate, the combination of protease and alcalase can be of interest to generate a more intense flavour.

Figure 4: Simplified schema of protein hydrolysate for use as flavouring agent.

More precisely, the process consists of a first mechanically size reduction of raw material, liquefaction of the subsequent material by enzymatic hydrolysis, thermal inactivation of the enzymes followed by centrifugation or filtration of bones, separation of oils, and concentration of the flavourings. The final product consists of dried powder of seafood flavouring. The drying can be performed with different technologies such as spray-drying or roller drum driers.

The main unit needed for the process are shown below.

Figure 5: Hydrolysis reactor (stirred batch reactor 250 l).

Figure 6: Industrial sieve for solids separation such as fish bones.

Figure 7: Decanter to separate solids, water and oil fraction.

The oily fraction can be stored in a tank, after the adequate dosage of an antioxidant or can be further refined. The solid is a fish protein concentrate partially hydrolysed. The fish protein hydrolysate is in the water fraction that is lately dried.

Figure 8: Spray-drying and roller drum driers units.

The details of the enzymes used, and process parameters are part of the products' specifications and recipes of each company, and the sensory quality of flavourings depends on several parameters where the specificity and the level of enzymes are important factors. Other factors such as the pre-

treatment of the raw material prior to hydrolysis, substrate to water ratio, pH, and temperature also play an important role.

3.1.3.2 Economic aspects

If we foresee the construction of a new facility for the use of 300 tonnes per year of Hakes under MRCS for the production a flavouring agent, taking into account all the incomes and expenses:

- investment needed: facilities and equipment
- the expenses of refrigerated conservation in harbour of the UUC
- logistics of the UUC from the harbour to the facilities,
- processing costs: materials, energy, personnel and other indirect costs
- incomes: selling the product

We can calculate the annual cash flow of the business during the amortization period estimating different costs of purchase of the UUC, from 0 €/t if we suppose the utility is built by the fishermen up to 600 €/t that makes the business unfeasible.

Figure 9: Cash flow of flavouring agent business for different raw material prices.

Main economic indicators for each option are reported in Table 5. The construction of a new facility close to the harbour for the production of “Hake Flavour” is feasible if the price of the raw material is under 524 €/t. However, to attain a discount rate of 5 % a maximum of 330 €/tn can be paid.

Table 5: Main economic feasibility figures for the production Hake flavour

Parameter	Unit					
Investment	€	1,910,000	1,910,000	1,910,000	1,910,000	1,910,000
Discount and loan interest rate	%	5	5	5	5	5
Amortization period	years	10	10	10	10	10
UUC acquisition price	€/tn	0	100	200	400	600
Total Expenses	€	372,323	402,323	432,323	492,323	552,323
Total Incomes	€	571,200	571,200	571,200	571,200	571,200
BCR		1.53	1.42	1.32	1.16	1.03
NPV	€	802,469	559,067	315,665	-171,138	-657,942
IRR	%	12.4	10.3	8.0	3.3	-2.2
ROI	%	20.4	18.8	17.3	14.1	11.0
PP	years	5.82	6.36	6.99	8.63	15.06

The payback period is over 5 years, which can be a drawback to attract investors or ask for a loan. However, if the valorisation is undertaken as “best available technique” for the management of these fractions, the participation of administrations can be expected, and therefore will reduce the interest rate of the loan and won’t require an elevated discount rate.

On the other hand, the calculation assumes a single shift and therefore the production can be increased by double, or more, shift that would improve the feasibility.

3.1.4 High quality fishmeal and fish oil

At any place where a substantial amount of UUC are landed the production of fishmeal (FM) and fish oil (FO) is an interesting possibility to get some value from that fraction. However, if a new facility is needed an economic feasibility study has to be done.

3.1.4.1 The process

The process to obtain these products has been detailed in the deliverable 6.2.

In brief, the 6 main steps of the process are

1. cooking for coagulation of the protein thereby liberating bound water and oil
2. separation by pressing of the coagulate yielding a solid phase (presscake) containing 60-80 % of the oil-free dry matter (protein, bones) and oil, and a liquid phase (press liquor) containing water and the rest of the solids (oil, dissolved and suspended protein, vitamins and minerals).
3. the press liquor is centrifugated in a decanter, to remove the main part of the sludge, and the oil is subsequently removed by centrifuge, and stored in tanks
4. stickwater is concentrated in multi-effect evaporators and the concentrate is thoroughly mixed with the presscake
5. the presscake, is dehydrated usually by two-stage drying
6. the dried material is milled and stored in bags or in bulk

Figure 10: Simplified schema of fishmeal and oil process

The equipment needed for fish meal and fish oil production is as follow:

Figure 11: Macerator for reducing the raw material to a homogeneous mince meat.

Figure 12: Appropriate pumps to move the fish paste from one equipment to other.

Figure 13: Screw drive cooker

The solid can be pressed, using single or double screw press, or fractions separated by a decanter (Figure 7).

Oil is then stored in a tank and can be further processed by clarification in a centrifuge and/or a vacuum drying. A pump is used to dose antioxidant to the oil.

A second tank is used for stickwater and is dried to concentrate the stickwater to recover soluble proteins and increasing the yield.

The solid fraction with the concentrated stickwater is pumped to a disc dryer. After the drying process an antioxidant dosing unit is situated to dose the final amount of antioxidant into the fish meal to ensure shelf stability.

The dried product is milled with a hammer mill and filled into bags.

Figure 14: Disc dryer

Market trends indicates that in 2025, fish meal and fish oil production should be 15 % higher compared with the 2013–15 average to meet the aquaculture demands, but about 96 % of the increase will stem from improved use of fish waste, cuttings and trimmings. FM produced from fish waste will represent 38 % of world FM production in 2025, that affect the composition and quality of the resulting FM and/or FO with, in general, less protein, more ash (minerals) and increased levels of small amino acids (such as glycine, proline, hydroxyproline) compared with those obtained from whole fish (FAO. 2016. The State of World Fisheries and Aquaculture 2016. Contributing to food security and nutrition for all. Rome. 200 pp).

On the other hand, FM prices increased significantly from 2006 to 2015, but since then, there has been a slight decline, even if prices have remained high (Figure 15). By 2025, the average FM price is expected to be up to 30 % lower (ca. 1000 €/tn). The average FO price is projected to decline by 21 % by 2025 but remain higher than FM prices.

Therefore, there is a market for the commercialization of high quality FM and FO produced from UUC and with a good forecast.

Figure 15: Fishmeal price from Peru (1st world producer) from January 1999 to January 2019. (Source: www.indexmundi.com)

3.1.4.2 Feasibility study

In the case study of Bay of Biscay taking the port of Ondarroa as an example, where 5000 t/year of UUC are expected, two possibilities can be foreseen. On the one hand, the utilization of the available infrastructures situated at 50 km from the port, in the other hand the construction of a new facility situated in, or close to, the port.

In Table 6 different scenarios were evaluated. The differences when doing the study are mainly focused in the transportation requirements (not needed for a new facility situated in or close to the harbour), the investment need (no investment need to use existing facilities) and the different prices for the raw material acquisition.

Table 6: Main economic feasibility figures for the production fishmeal and fish oil

Parameter	Unit	Existing facility		New Facility		
Investment	€	0	0	1,660,000	1,660,000	1,660,000
Discount and loan interest rate	%	5	5	5	5	5
Amortization period	years	-	-	10	10	10
UUC acquisition price	€/tn	100	200	0	100	200
Total Expenses	€	847,156	1,347,156	477,882	977,882	1,477,882
Total Incomes	€	1,750,000	1,750,000	1,750,000	1,750,000	1,750,000
BCR		2.07	1.30	3.66	1.79	1.18
NPV	€	7,266,398	3,209,701	9,574,190	5,517,493	1,460,796
IRR	%	-	-	83.2	52.7	19.7
ROI	%	-	-	86.6	56.5	26.4
PP	years	-	-	1.22	1.92	4.41

Using the same methodology, one can calculate the maximum price that can be paid for the existing facility, making the 10 year earning equal to 0 €, that is 279 €/t. Also, the purchase price that makes benefit of fishmeal producer and fisher equal can be calculated: 140 €/t.

On the other hand, the maximum value that can be paid for the UUC for a new plant situated close to the harbour is 246 €/t.

By doing a relative change in the input values (the purchasing price of the raw material (RM), the price of the energy and the changes in the selling price of the products) we can evaluate their effects on the economic parameters.

Table 7: Effect of relative changes of the variables in the feasibility

Scenarios (relative changes)								
Amount of raw material	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
RM price	1	0.75	1.25	1	1	1	1	1.25
Products price	1	1	1	0.75	1.25	1	1	0.75
Energy price	1	1	1	1	1	0.75	1.25	1.25
Economic parameters								
NPV (k€)	5,517	6,532	4,503	1,983	9,052	5,805	5,23	681
IRR	53 %	60 %	45 %	24 %	79 %	55 %	50 %	12 %
ROI	57 %	64 %	49 %	30 %	83 %	59 %	54 %	20 %
PP	1.92	1.68	2.24	3.80	1.28	1.84	2.00	5,84

In Table 7 we can see that for a same change in 25 % of the value, the most sensitive value is the selling price of the fishmeal and fish oil. However, in the worse scenario evaluated, increase of 25 % in energy and raw material prices and decrease of 25 % in selling prices the investment would still be profitable with a PP of less than 6 years.

Others different scenarios can be evaluated if we assume a lower amount of UUC due to the improvement of gear selectivity or fishing strategies. This parameter is even more sensitive than the selling price, but with a 50 % of decrease the investment still profitable.

Table 8: Effect of relative changes of the variables in the feasibility (2)

Scenarios (relative changes)						
Amount of raw material	0.75	0.50	0.75	0.75	0.75	0.75
RM price	1	1	1	1	1.25	1.25
Products price	1	1	0.75	1	1	0.75
Energy price	1	1	1	1.25	1	1.25
NPV (k€)	3,298	1,080	648	3,083	2,538	-328
IRR	35.3 %	16.2 %	11.9 %	33.5 %	29.0 %	1.0 %
ROI	39.9 %	23.3 %	20.2 %	38.3 %	34.3 %	12.9 %
PP	2.81	5.04	5.93	2.92	3.34	9.53

In this case if we evaluate the worse scenario, decrease in raw material of 25 %, increase of 25 % in energy and raw material prices and decrease of 25 % in selling prices the result is no longer profitable.

3.1.5 Conclusions

Three different solutions were evaluated for the valorisation of UUC in the Bay of Biscay. The production of fish burgers, or other fish preparation, with catches above the MRCS is a viable solution that can at the same time help increase the fish consumption in different sectors. For the catches under MRCS the production of fish flavouring agents may represent a very valuable valorisation option. For the processing of a high quantity of UUC the production of high quality of fish meal and fish oil represents a profitable solution that remains interesting even in less favourable scenarios.

3.2 North Sea case study

3.2.1 Methodology

The economic feasibility of the North Sea and Skagerrak case study was investigated using interviews with potential buyers of UUC fish and by comparison of potential prices derived for UUC depending on buyers held against the cost of landing UUC for fishers.

3.2.2 Fishmeal and fish oil

Two major companies dominate the fishmeal market in Denmark: “TripleNine” and “FF Skagen”. Local small scale production of fishmeal do occur but is of minor importance for the fishmeal market. Located in Hanstholm, the “FF Skagen” subsidiary “FF Hanstholm” is the most obvious partner for taking UUC fish at the Port of Hanstholm.

Interviews with several employees from “FF Hanstholm” were conducted as well as the attendance of a “FF Hansholm” employee at a workshop regarding the handling and usage of UUC at the Port of Hanstholm. Additionally, dialogue with the Danish branch organization “Marine Ingredients” which represent the producers of fishmeal and fish oil in Denmark have been ongoing in the project.

Fishmeal producers do see UUC as an obvious supplement to the current resource and would like to take this in. There is no expectation of specific challenges in the increased amount of resource uptake from UUC in their production.

Depending of the species, fishmeal producers are willing to set the price of UUC fish at roughly the current level of 2.00 DKK/kg. The view of the fishmeal producers is that it is unlikely that a higher price can be given for UUC fish intended for fishmeal than the price given to industrial fishers.

In the event that some of the UUC species have a low content of oil or do not have the right composition of proteins, it is possible that the price level for UUC fish will be lower than that of industrial fish.

The landing, handling and processing of industrial fish and products from this as will consolidated in Denmark. In 2016, more than 90 % of all Danish industrial fish landings occurred in the four harbours

Thyborøn, Skagen, Hanstholm and Hvide Sande. The processing of the resource to fishmeal and fish oil is done in Thyborøn, Skagen and Hanstholm. In order to keep costs for logistics and transport it is essential that UUC landings occur close to one of these processing facilities.

3.2.3 Feed for the fur industry

Production of fodder for fur (mainly mink) take a significant amount of industrial fish in Denmark and thereby a potential buyer of UUC fish. In Denmark, 14 mink feed centrals produce 99 % of all the feed for the fur industry. All of these are organized under “Dansk Pelsdyr Foder a.m.b.a” which is the trade organisation for Danish fur industry feed. Uptake, import and distribution of resources for feed production is coordinated through this trade organisation.

The production of mink fur has been in growth in Denmark through several years, with approx. 18 million mink produces in 2016, compared to 13.5 million in 2006. In addition to the increased number of minks, the production has also shifted to production of large sizes of mink, meaning that the production and feeding period has increased. More feed is therefore needed per mink per year; the required feed need has thereby increased from roughly 33 kg per mink per year to 47 kg per mink per year during the last 15 years.

Fish constitute roughly 40 % of the mink feed, either as fresh fish supplied directly from a port, frozen fish from other countries such as Iceland or the Faroe Islands or in as cut-offs or wastage from a fish processing facility. The natural diet of mink mainly consists of fish and it is important for the quality of the fur. Different raw material from animals and plants constitute the remaining 60 % of mink feed.

Specific requirements apply to the fish resource used in the production of mink as a significant amount of fresh fodder of high quality is needed. Therefore, mink fodder producers are willing to pay a higher price for fish than that of the price given for fish intended for fishmeal or fish oil.

3.2.4 Pet food

The pet food industry consists of several large international food producers of which several have production facilities in the Netherlands and Germany. These producers use fishmeal and fish cut-off for the pet food production. Several minor Danish producers exist that base their production on whole fish or cut-off which is processed and added to the final pet food products in different quantities.

Dry pet food for dogs and cats mainly contain fishmeal and fish oil for certain producers. Most producers of dry pet food buy fishmeal from the fishmeal producers and add their own feed mixture in ranging quantities. For this pet food type, the fish species and origin has no interest and UUC fish would only serve as a share of the fishmeal production.

Some pet food brands want to separate their product from the rest by having a higher focus on the usage of certain species or by guaranteeing a higher quality for their product. UUC catches may be relevant for this specific segment and there is a willingness to pay a higher price for raw materials among these pet food producers too.

A few of the interviewed pet food producers believed UUC catches could be of interest to their pet food production. However, price and quality are of great importance and the logistic arrangements currently in use in the business may be difficult to rearrange. Several suppliers of the raw material have a large influence and the input and accordingly it is rarely the demand from food producers that secure new input material to the pet food production.

Several interviewed company representatives stressed that there is a high focus in the pet food industry on securing a low level of harmful substances, especially heavy metals, in the fish material used for production. Dogs and cats consume a substantial share of fish whereby an increased level of harmful substances will lead to bioaccumulation throughout the animal's life. Especially fatty fish species were pointed to as the best fish input for pet food due to their high oil content. However, because heavy metals as well as other harmful substances tend to accumulate in fat tissue, the fish species with a high fat content will also be the most prone to higher levels of harmful substances compared to leaner species with a lower fat content. Overall, the level of heavy metals and thereby in the fish inhabiting the water body has been higher in the Baltic Sea, Inner Danish waters and Kattegat compared to for instance the North Sea. This is known in the feed and pet food industry and this may be a challenge for the usage of UUC catches from these areas.

Some pet food producers prefer to procure the fish in blocks of ice and rarely pay more for the resource than fur industry feed producers. Most of the time there is an overlap in the species used by the fur industry feed producers and any additional payment would be to cover the costs of freezing and potential transport-related costs.

Engagement with the different pet food producers has not resulted in a cooperation for the usage of UUC catches. This is primarily due to the lack in amount of landed UUC, way below the threshold level for a stable supply in the specific industry.

4 Conclusions and perspectives

- The overall conclusion based on interviews done in Denmark, France and Spain, is that the expected amount of UUC fish is much less than what was estimated in 2015
- There are buyers ready to process the landed UUC fish, if they have the right quality and amount
- There are several solutions that are feasible and profitable
- Lack of knowledge of the amount of landed UUC fish makes the buyers unsustain and block for further investments
- Amount and economic (price of the fish) due to the Landing Obligation are a central key to reach the relevant threshold level, so both the flow of fish and the development can be steady and sustainable
- The level of expenditures to logistic, handling and processing are a challenge that have no straight forward answer – that blocks investments
- There has been a change in the behavior of the fishermen activities and their fishing pattern to avoid the UUC fish

- 2017 and 2018 were expected to be the years that gave the answer to some of the questions, but that has not happened